

The Imamate Doctrine: A Historical Exploration of Its Evolution and Significance

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Abstract

Some modernist Muslim and non-Muslim intellectual currents in Shi'a thought have been doing critical research for about a hundred years, especially in the last two or three decades. They are trying to show that some basic Shi'a beliefs about how we know things are unstable and based on historical events instead of the Quran and Prophetic tradition. The consequence of this perspective is that what Shi'ites have believed throughout different periods since their inception, at least in those aspects where they do not align with other Muslims, is sometimes viewed as fabricated or based on their efforts to maintain their position in various arenas (history as a constructor of beliefs). An example of this is the discussion surrounding the concept of imamate and the endowment of the Prophet's successors with knowledge, infallibility, and divine designation. In contrast, there exists an alternative viewpoint that, by grounding itself in the Quran and the same narration sources and employing the methods of the ancients in validating narrations, endeavors to present an alternative hypothesis. This hypothesis utilizes the most effective method in terms of historical research methodology (the descriptive-explanatory method, which leads to the realization of religious understanding and its path recognition) [3] and, by considering the role of influential historical elements—political, social, cultural, and economic—demonstrates the application of the summary-detailed explanation of the Imamate doctrine within the societal context from a narrative perspective. This viewpoint encompasses three fundamental discussions: first, the theoretical and Quranic foundations and the question of why a summary and detailed explanation is necessary; second, outlining how historical elements play a role; and third, the comparative presentation of the explanation of the principle of imamate within the summary-detailed framework, which is the objective of this study.

Keywords: Shi'a thought, modernist intellectual currents, imamate doctrine, historical context, Quranic foundations

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Introduction

The principle of Imamate, a fundamental concept in Shia theology, went through four distinct periods that signified its progressive development. Each phase marked an advanced stage, beginning with an introductory summary and culminating in an exhaustive elucidation as follows.

1. The Initial Phase:

- Extending from the time of the Prophet of Islam to the end of Imam Sajjad's (peace be upon him) Imamate, this period laid the foundational tenets of the doctrine.
- During this phase, the Imams established the core principles of Imamate, emphasizing the divine designation of the Imam as the successor to the Prophet and the infallible guide for the Muslim community.
- This period primarily focused on introducing and establishing the concept of Imamate and its significance in ensuring the preservation and propagation of Islam.

2. The Period of Proliferation:

- Encompassing the Imamate of the Two Sadiqs (peace be upon them), this phase witnessed the proliferation and intellectual expansion of Imamic knowledge.
- With the increased persecution and political restrictions faced by the Imams, they shifted their focus from public activism to scholarly pursuits.
- The Imams engaged in extensive teaching and intellectual discourse, disseminating essential Islamic sciences, including theology, jurisprudence, and spirituality.

3. The Consolidation Phase:

- Characterized by the Imamate of Imam Kazim and Imam Reza (peace be upon them), this phase witnessed the consolidation and rectification of the Imamate doctrine.
- The Imams faced intense intellectual challenges from various theological schools, necessitating the codification and refinement of Imamiyyah beliefs.
- They engaged in debates and authored works that refuted opposing views and solidified the foundations of Imamiyyah theology.

4. The Final Phase:

- Extending from the Imamate of Imam Jawad (peace be upon him) until the onset of the Occultation, this period was marked by the perpetuation and further refinement of the Imamate principles.
- The Imams continued to disseminate their teachings and establish scholarly institutions, ensuring the preservation and transmission of imamic knowledge.
- This phase also saw the gradual transition to the concept of the Occultation of the Imam, preparing the Shia community for the absence of a physically present Imam.

These distinct phases encapsulate the evolutionary trajectory of the Imamate doctrine, explicating its maturation from rudimentary foundations to a thoroughly articulated theological framework that continues to guide and inspire Shia Muslims to this day.

Historical Elements and the Explanation of the Principle of Imamate

By considering the role of historical elements and reflecting upon the narrations concerning Imamate, in addition to identifying the three necessary conditions for accepting an Imam (knowledge, infallibility, and designation), we can categorize them into three groups and modes of expression. The presentation of this categorization, as will be seen, is a summary in the first period but becomes more detailed in later periods. These three categories are as follows.

1. The first category consists of narrations that directly and explicitly address the topic of imamate, albeit in the form of single words. The narrations containing these terms, in the first period, lack any elaboration or emphasis on a specific characteristic. However, in later periods, these narrations were numerous and used with greater detail, such as the noble Hadith of Wilayah (authority).
2. The second category comprises texts that, although not as explicitly worded as the first category and using different terms, their overall content yields the same conclusion as the first category through a kind of implied and indirect indication. Examples include the noble verse of purification, which implies infallibility, and the comprehensive Hadith of Thaqaalayn.
3. The third category consists of various types of texts that speak of the importance and high status of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them), namely the narrations of the virtues of Imam Ali and the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them), such as the Hadith of Tayr al-Mashawi (the roasted bird).

It is for sure clear that a solely virtue-based perspective on this category of narrations is a superficial view and cannot accurately convey the depth of the matter. By considering the entirety of these narrations, a conclusion is reached that is very close to the semantic outcome of the previous two categories. Similarly, a comprehensive examination of all three categories clarifies the proof of the matter.

Explanation of the Principle of Imamate in Four Periods

As mentioned earlier, four periods can be considered in explaining the principle of imamate. These four periods, along with the nature of the narrations presented in each, are as follows:

The Period from the Prophet (peace be upon him and his progeny) to the End of Imam Sajjad's Imamate

Although the initial summary explanation of the principle of imamate began with the early days of Islam's emergence, the misalignment of historical elements during this period, particularly in instances such as the political repression prevalent in society during the first three caliphs, the issue of new Muslims, the lack of social standing of the Ahl al-Bayt (peace be upon them), and the absence of a scholarly and inquisitive group among the companions of the Prophet (peace be upon him), caused the explanation of the concept of imamate in broader society to largely remain within its summary limits for about a century. It is evident that, considering the set of historical elements that emerged during this time, the detailed explanation of this fundamental principle, taking into account its various dimensions and conveying it to the general public, required the passage of time and the emergence of suitable conditions.

Therefore, in the first step, the emphasis of the Prophet of Islam, as the most important teacher of this principle, and also the early Imams in this period, with a summary explanation, should be on the essence of the matter of imamate along with the designation of a specific instance of it, in order to compare the characteristics in later periods. Hence, the summary explanation of the issue of Imamate, in the form of the succession of Imam Ali (peace be upon him) and without extensive explanation, was done in a way that considered the possibility and level of understanding of the general public. Ultimately, it was accompanied by a limited understanding from the audience, confined to a simple spiritual concept (successor of the Prophet), and there was no further expansion, especially for the general public. Although one can point to detailed instances, such as examples from the book of Salim ibn Qays, which were discussed at a level beyond the public sphere and for specific individuals like Salman, Abu Dharr, Jabir ibn Abdullah al-Ansari, and others, even some others, like the second caliph, as

evidenced by his dispute with Ibn Abbas in the gathering regarding prophet hood and caliphate, understood it. [49]

On the other hand, although the abundance of texts from this period pertains to the lifetime of the Prophet of Islam (peace be upon him and his progeny), the multiplicity of texts and distinct Quranic and narrational reports, in terms of the use of foundational terms and single words, is greater in this approximately century-long period than in any other period. These texts and reports are mostly presented as short statements with limited vocabulary and in formats such as poetry, sermons, supplications, and debates, without any explanation. An example is what was mentioned in Lady Fatima's (peace be upon her) sermon about the principle of imamate, where imamate was introduced as the "order of religion" and "protection from division." [50]

Derivatives of words such as "caliphate," "imamate," "wilayah" (authority), "leadership," "successorship," and "inheritance" are frequently repeated examples in this period, alongside texts from two other categories, such as the verses of Mubahila (Al Imran/61), Mawadda (Shura/23), Tathir (Ahzab/33), and the narrations of Taysr (bird), Safina (ship), [51] Nujum (stars), [52] Madinat al-Ilm (city of knowledge), [53] the granting of the Liwa (banner), [54] and others, play a role in establishing a profound but simple semantic foundation. [55] Although Imam Ali (peace be upon him) is the focus in some of these narrations, the crucial element in all of them is the expression of qualifications and characteristics that are only realised in the person of the Imam.

Instances from the Quran

Verses pertaining to guardianship (Ma'edah/55), imamate (Baqarah/124), those vested with authority (Nisa/59), and charity (Mujadalah/13) are among the renowned verses addressing the concepts of guardianship, imamate, and authority. However, these verses lack explicit elucidation of their profound implications. In instances where Imam Ali (PBUH) alluded to the circumstances surrounding the revelation of some of these verses, he refrained from providing explanations, limiting himself to a political interpretation. For example, the first explanations of the meaning of the verse about people in charge, even though it seemed to have a clear meaning, came about during the time of Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT), based on the idea that people would obey them. Similarly, the earliest inquiries into the meaning of "Laa Yanal 'Ahd al-Zalimeen" (My covenant does not include the wrongdoers) in the verse on Imamate also surfaced during their era.

Instances from Narrations

Caliphate

When the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) publicly declared his mission in the third year of his prophetic calling, during the incident of the Day of Warning (ash-Shu'ara/214), he offered the position of ministry to approximately thirty of his close relatives in exchange for their recognition of him as their brother, successor, and caliph. As evidenced by the nature of this gathering, the focus was solely on the conventional meanings of the terms, with no intention of delving deeper, and no questions were raised about their profound significance.

Following this event, the Prophet (PBUH), on various occasions such as the Night of the Jinn Delegation, the Battle of Tabuk, the Hadith of Position, the Twelve Caliphs, and the Hadith of the Two Weighty Things, employed the term "caliph" in a general manner without providing a detailed explanation of its meaning. Only in the latter instance, the Prophet (PBUH) reiterated three times the phrase "I remind you of God concerning my family."

Furthermore, regarding the twelve successors, most texts reporting on the Prophet, aside from a brief mention of their Qurayshi lineage, do not mention their names. Although in

some other narrations, particularly Shia narrations, there is mention of the description or names of these twelve individuals, most of these narrations pertain to accounts from Imams of later periods who have themselves narrated these traditions from the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). This reality indicates the non-comprehensive and private nature of these teachings in the early period. Therefore, only in some narrations, in addition to referring to the twelve successors, are the names of some of them—three or four individuals—explicitly mentioned, while the rest are identified with phrases like "and those born from Hussain," "all of them from Quraysh," or "leaders of the Children of Israel." Moreover, at times, a deeper understanding of this matter remains unanswered.

The late Saduq, in analysing this brevity, emphasises that while Shia scholars have made every effort to document such hadiths, it cannot be claimed that all Shias, or even some of their elite, were aware of the names of the Imams. Apparently in such cases, the highest interpretation of the concept of caliphate was political succession. This is supported by a conversation that took place between the Prophet (PBUH) and the Bani Amir, where they set a condition for their assistance to the Prophet regarding the matter of succession.

Guardianship

Similarly, in the collection of narrations where the term "Wali" (guardian) is used, such as "You are the guardian of every believer after me," the general understanding and perception are such that the depth of this term's meaning is not grasped, and anything beyond it is not tolerated. For example, one can refer to the widely-known event of Ghadir Khumm; the manner of its expression was unprecedented to that day, even prompting the revelation of the verse of Tabligh (communication). The use of the term "Mawla" in this narration and the lack of explanation of the said term by the Prophet (PBUH), without considering the context of its issuance, led to its complexity and the emergence of several other possible meanings. Even the Imams in this period, at most, intended a political interpretation in the position of appointing an Islamic ruler from this narration, as Imam Hussain (PBUH) explicitly did in his analysis of Muawiyah's governmental behaviour.

Imamate and Knowledge

There is another set of well-known narrations where these terms are employed. Examples include the succinctness in the narrations of "Medina of Knowledge," Imam Ali's (PBUH) statement regarding his Quranic knowledge, Imam Hassan's (PBUH) sermon after the martyrdom of Imam Ali (PBUH), the incident of Yemen, and a part of Fatima's sermon that has been narrated with various expressions. The majority of these instances of brevity arose due to the social conditions and temporal necessities during the lives of the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT).

Inheritance and Bequest

Texts containing the terms "wasiyyah" (bequest) and "wirathah" (inheritance) are significant for two reasons: first, they were mentioned repeatedly and on various occasions throughout the twenty-three years of the Prophet's (PBUH) mission. Second, the question arises as to what the terms "wasiyyah" and "wirathah" encompass.

In the Quranic verses, the root word "wasiyy" appears eighteen times, with the verb "wasiyya" used only twice (ash-Shura/13), both emphasising piety and establishing religion as the subject of the bequest. The remaining instances relate to material matters. Moreover, in the Quranic verses, the root word "wirath" appears thirty-four times, with three themes: inheritance of property, inheritors of the earth, and inheritors of the Book (Fatir/32), which Imam al-Baqir (PBUH) later interprets. There are many hadiths about the Prophets that use

the words "wasiyyah" and "wirathah," and their meanings are often vague and general. For example, in the Hadith of Brotherhood, Imam Ali (PBUH) introduced himself as "the successor of the successors," and in "among them are the bequest and inheritance," Imam Hassan (PBUH) said, "I am the son of the successor," and on the day of Ashura, Imam Hussain (PBUH) asked, "Am I not the son of the daughter of your Prophet, the son of his successor, and the son of his cousin?" These are just a few examples.

Infallibility

As previously mentioned, the verse of infallibility and its revelation concerning the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT) signifies a profound content within the prophetic teachings. However, explicitly stating this knowledge is beyond the grasp of the general public. Therefore, the Prophet (PBUH) and the early Imams (PBUT) consistently employed brevity and utilized words that, alongside their primary meaning, allowed for other interpretations to some extent, or they expressed it through specific examples to gradually guide minds towards its true meaning. Numerous Prophetic phrases like "He is with the truth, and the truth is with him" and "May God have mercy on Ali; O God, turn the truth with him wherever it turns," along with some references and themes from the Imams (PBUT), indicate the gradual revelation of this profound content. For instance, Imam Hassan (PBUH), and in another case, Imam Sajjad (PBUH), while introducing the status of the Imam, his distance from all forms of impurity and defilement, and his possession of a higher position compared to others, emphasized this characteristic using the term "infallibility."

The Era of Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT)

Undoubtedly, the opportunity for disseminating knowledge during this period was greater than in any other era. However, the Imams faced two fundamental challenges: first, due to the prevailing conditions in the previous era, Muslims' awareness of Islamic laws and beliefs, including the Imam's position in the order of creation, remained at a basic level. Second, with the weakening of the Umayyad dynasty and the political activities among rival groups, the desire to seize political power increased, and it was natural for the public to expect the Imams (PBUT), given past failures, to enter this conflict. This was because all groups fighting against the Umayyads were advancing their cause under the slogan of Ahl al-Bayt's (PBUT) eligibility for the caliphate. This, coupled with their lack of proper understanding of the Imam's position and duties, led to the emergence of splinter groups. However, with the fulfilment of the political predictions of Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT) and their success in clarifying their positions and educating a vast number of students, these splinter groups were marginalized.

In this situation, Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT), taking advantage of the alignment of most influential historical elements, took steps towards the correct explanation of the concept and knowledge system of Imamate and endeavoured to present an accurate picture of the meaning of Imamate, which was the succession of the Prophet in matters beyond political rule. They strived to utilise and transcend the texts of the past era and, based on the same established foundations, skillfully disseminate detailed explanations of previous hadiths through inquisitive narrators in Medina, Kufa, Aleppo, and other cities, in public and private gatherings, debates, and also during Hajj pilgrimages, especially in Mecca and Mina.

After Imam Ali (PBUH), the majority of the people of Medina pledged allegiance to Imam Hassan (PBUH) as the caliph, based on their belief in his designation as the successor. Similarly, in the well-known dispute between Muhammad ibn al-Hanafiyyah and Imam Sajjad (PBUH), Muhammad acknowledged the guardianship of Imam Ali (PBUH) and Hassan and

Hussain (PBUT) as the successors of the Prophet. The content of narrations during this period presents the following concepts:

- "Imamate" is viewed as a divine gift, transferred before the demise of the previous Imam, as per the Prophet's explicit instructions, to the designated successor.
- The Imam is regarded as possessing knowledge surpassing that of others, derived from unique sources and transmitted through a form of inheritance.
- The Imam is considered infallible and shielded from sin and error.
- It is not obligatory for the divinely appointed imam to immediately rise and assert his political rights upon appointment. He enters the political arena when a sufficient portion of society possesses awareness and understanding of the Imam's rights, and the need for the Imam reaches its peak, prompting them to seek his leadership and establish an Islamic government based on Islamic principles. In this part of the study, we examine some of these aspects.

Designation (nass) and Appointment (nashb)

However, this concept became prevalent during the time of Imam al-Baqir (PBUH). In one account, when asked how people can identify the next Imam after the demise of the current one, the Imam refers to "wasiyyah" (bequest) as the "acknowledgment of the Ahl al-Bayt's (PBUT) virtue" by the next Imam. However, in another instance, the Imam provides a detailed explanation to the same narrator regarding the designation and appointment of each Imam. A historical report from this period also indicates that the government of Hisham became fearful of the widespread acceptance of this belief. Additionally, Mansur's pursuit of finding the person to whom Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH) had bequeathed his knowledge further demonstrates the prevalence of this belief.

Knowledge

With the relative improvement of conditions towards the end of Imam al-Sajjad's (PBUH) time, the dissemination of certain knowledge flourished. Imam al-Sajjad (PBUH), stating that knowledge is found only with the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT), described them as the "treasury of knowledge." Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT) introduced knowledge and awareness of all matters as one of the essential requirements for imamate and emphasized that a certain type of knowledge never diminishes and is passed down through inheritance to the next imamate.

During the time of Imam al-Baqir (PBUH), the concept of knowledge expanded with an explanation of the "City of Knowledge," moving away from its previous brevity. The account of Shanid ibn Abi Hafsa from Imam al-Baqir (PBUH), detailing the nature of the thousand doors of knowledge and how only one or two doors have been opened to people so far, clearly demonstrates the growing trend of clarification. In another instance, the Imam states that the extent of knowledge inherited from the Prophet among the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT) is the knowledge of all the prophets, past and future.

In another example, Dharriss al-Kanassi narrates from the Imam (PBUH): "Do you think that God Almighty has made obedience to His guardians and friends obligatory upon His servants but has concealed from them the news of the heavens and the earth and deprived them of the source of knowledge regarding matters that uphold their religion?" These reports clearly indicate the growing understanding of "Imam's knowledge" among the community. The Imam's explicit statement, "They criticise this about the one whom God has given the proof of the truth of our knowledge," in this narration clearly reveals this fact. In the era of Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH), these explanations reached their peak of detail, and the sources of the Imam's profound knowledge and its tools were presented and clarified, at least in three branches: direct divine knowledge, knowledge transmitted from the Prophet (PBUH),

and knowledge received through the spirit and angels. The Holy Spirit, Jama'ah (community), Mushaf of Fatimah (PBUH), scriptures and books of the prophets, pillar of light, a thousand doors, Hadith, Quran, the Greatest Name, Jafr Ahmar (Red Jafr), Jafr Abyad (White Jafr), Jafr Asghar (Smaller Jafr), and Jafr Akbar (Greater Jafr) are examples of these titles, sometimes presented together and sometimes individually. Although it seems that Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH) initially expressed these matters to the elite, the abundance of narrators and questions, along with the Imam's lack of admonition about the confidentiality of these words, indicates his approval of their public dissemination. In one of these gatherings, sixty people were present. Examples of these details, which had become well-known among the general public, can be seen in the questions of the companions to Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH) or in narrations describing the sources of the Imam's knowledge.

Knowledge of the Unseen

Besides sources of knowledge, the scope of the imam's knowledge is also a notable topic. Based on Quranic teachings, knowledge is categorized into various types, one of which is called "Ilm al-Ghayb" (knowledge of the unseen). This knowledge is considered exclusive to God or denied to others. However, based on another set of verses that mention the bestowal of knowledge of the unseen upon prophets and even non-prophets, the question of the Imams' access to divine knowledge of the unseen and its compatibility with the exclusivity of such knowledge to God is an important issue that was publicly raised during this period, unlike the previous era.

Although Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH) disagrees with the idea that the Imam knows things about the unseen, he does explain that the unseen has different forms, with some forms being exclusive to God and others being superhuman. He does, however, affirm the existence of the extensive knowledge that God bestowed upon the Imams (PBUT).

The narrations of Sudir and Abu Basir are famous examples of the Imam's efforts to affirm and prevent extremist and deviant aspects of this topic. Nevertheless, the general belief in the principle of such stations, stemming from the extensive knowledge of the Imams (PBUT), was widespread during this period.

Infallibility

Since people didn't talk about infallibility much back then, it was only used in a few places. For example, in some prayers of the Sahifa al-Sajjadiyya that were later made public, or in a story that Imam al-Sajjad (PBUH) told about the conditions of infallibility and the link between the Quran, infallibility, and the Imam. It was probably told to his close friends and then made public by Imam al-Kadhim (PBUH). Nevertheless, the dissemination of the conceptual content of infallibility during the time of Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT) cannot be overlooked. For example, Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH), in a sermon, elaborates on various aspects of the infallibility of the Imams.

Ibn Ashqar also inquired from Hisham ibn Hakam about the Shia belief that "only an infallible person can be an imam"—the same statement made by Imam al-Sajjad (PBUH). Hisham, in response, said:

"I asked Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH) about it, and he said: 'With the help and support of God, he refrains from any action that God has forbidden, and God Almighty has said: "And whoever holds fast to Allah has indeed been guided to a straight path."'"

A similar statement is also narrated in the account of A'mash from Imam al-Sadiq (PBUH):

"The prophets and their successors have no sins because they are infallible and purified."

Ibn Abi 'Umayr, a prominent Shia narrator, considers Hisham's argument for infallibility as the best he has heard and learned from him. In this argument, Hisham negates four qualities of the Imam: greed, envy, anger, and lust. Apparently he derived this argument from a report from Imam Ali (PBUH) on the same subject.

The Imam's distance from all prohibitions and unworthiness incompatible with Imamate is the same meaning derived from the verse of purification and the verse of Imamate. Additionally, some terms like "Musaddad" (supported) and "Muwaffaq" (successful) carry the same semantic weight, sometimes expressed by Imam al-Rida (PBUH). With this consideration, it can be understood that the topics of knowledge and infallibility reached a stage of consolidation during this period.

The Era of Imams Musa al-Kazim and Ali al-Rida (PBUT): Consolidation and Refinement of Thought

In this period, which lasted until around 203 AH, a more comprehensive and profound explanation of the concept of imamate, compared to the previous era, can be observed in the form of responses to emerging doubts. Thus, the knowledge system of Imamate was completed and prepared for practical implementation in the period before the occultation. However, the 35-year period of Imam al-Kazim (PBUH) was mostly spent in confinement and imprisonment, and the Shias were unaware of the Imam's well-being for some time, even leading some to speculate about his potential status as the Qa'im (the awaited saviour).

Under these circumstances, most affairs were conducted through the Imam's close associates, such as Ali ibn Yaqtin and Hisham ibn Hakam, along with the network of representatives, under the Imam's supervision. Meanwhile, answering some questions was delegated to the companions. The report of Hammad about Imam al-Kazim's instruction to Muhammad ibn Hakim regarding answering questions in the mosque is a clear example of this. This policy of the Imam was highly successful, to the extent that its reflection can be seen in the following narration: Muhammad ibn Hakim says:

"I said to Imam Musa al-Kazim (PBUH): 'May I be sacrificed for you! We have become knowledgeable in religion, and God has made us independent of people through you. So much so that if a group of us are present in a gathering, no man asks his friend a question unless he knows the matter and its answer, thanks to the blessing that God has bestowed upon us through you.'"

This important task was continued during the time of Imam al-Rida (PBUH) with the emergence of the conflict between Amin and Ma'mun and subsequently the issue of the crown prince, in the form of questions and answers and resolving doubts. In particular, the Imam endeavored to transform the emerging scholarly atmosphere into a self-sufficient community by referring Shias to prominent scholars like Yunus ibn Abd al-Rahman and Muhammad ibn Abi 'Umayr. Ibn Abi 'Umayr alone authored ninety-four books, including "al-Ihtijaj fi al-Imamah" (The Argumentation on Imamate).

Designation, Knowledge, and Infallibility

It was said that the Imams consider divine designation and selection as essential and have mentioned ways to understand them, even citing signs like knowing various languages as a virtue of the Imam.

In this period, numerous reports are available about efforts to find the name of the designated Imam after Imam al-Kazim (PBUH), especially with the passing of Ismail and Imam al-Sadiq's (PBUH) will regarding him after his demise. Also, Imam al-Rida (PBUH), who had no children until the last decade of his life, was repeatedly asked about his successor. The Imam, citing two verses (Maryam/12 and Yusuf/22) and comparing them to Jesus

speaking in the cradle, guided the Shias towards the young Imam. Except for some Shias who were not from Medina and found it difficult to understand this matter, others accepted it. However, by the following year, with numerous questions to Imam al-Jawad (PBUH), the doubts were resolved, and the Imam spoke in detail about the aspects of the Imamate of the young Imam.

The argument of Imam al-Rida (PBUH) indicates the lack of a relationship between the Imam's age and his knowledge. The details and reflection of this argument in Ibn Salt's words among Shia scholars regarding the knowledge of the young Imam are as follows:

"If his imamate is from God, even if he is a one-day-old infant, he is like an elder, and if it is not from God, even if he has lived for a thousand years, he is like other people."

Moreover, Ma'mun himself was aware of this matter. He reminded those who had been defeated in debate with the young Imam that the Prophet (PBUH) had taken allegiance from Hassan and Hussain (PBUT) in their childhood, and there is no difference between their first and last.

Regarding the topic of infallibility, Imam al-Kazim and Imam al-Rida (PBUT), along with their companions, explained this concept in various situations, sometimes in the presence of non-Shias or where they had access to it.

For example, Imam al-Kazim (PBUH), quoting a narration from Imam al-Sajjad (PBUH), calls the Imams the "mines of infallibility."

In the debate between Hisham and Dirar, Hisham, by raising subsidiary issues, revisits the concept of infallibility and proves that there is no choice but the existence of a Hujjah (proof) with specific qualities. Then, citing the verse of purification, he explains the reasoning behind infallibility:

"Only the third option remains, which is for the Prophet (PBUH) to appoint a successor for himself who will guide them (the people), not make mistakes or deviate from the truth, not oppress, be infallible from sin, and not commit any errors. Everyone needs him in religious matters, but he does not need anyone."

Other examples of this kind can be seen in the meeting of Yazid ibn Salit with Imam al-Kazim (PBUH) on the way to Umrah and a statement by Imam al-Rida (PBUH) about adhering to the Imams, where, using expressions like "pure Imams" and "they are the infallible ones," points about the Imam's infallibility are made.

A Comprehensive Discussion on Imamate and its Attributes

The alignment of historical elements in a short period during the time of Imam al-Rida (PBUH)—especially with the Imam's presence in Khorasan and the emergence of an atmosphere of questioning, debate, and referring to him—along with the Imam's involvement in the crown prince affair—greatly contributed to the development and dissemination of reasoned and profound theological topics, such as Imamate.

The narration of the "Golden Chain" hadith and the surrounding events, as well as Abd al-Aziz ibn Muslim's statement in Merv about the widespread disagreement among people and their investigations into the matter of Imamate, clearly demonstrate the expansion of the discourse on Imamate. In response to him, the Imam explained important points, particularly regarding designation, knowledge, and infallibility. The Imam, emphasising the texts of the previous era, such as the verse of completion and the event of Ghadir Khumm, spoke about the divine designation and appointment of the Imams and their position concerning the people. He introduced the completeness of the Quran and the Prophet's (PBUH) not omitting any explanations as contingent upon the divine appointment of the Imam, an Imamate that was granted to Abraham (PBUH) after his prophet hood and being a friend of God, and continued in his "pure and purified offspring." The Imam, citing the Quran, referred to the hereditary

transfer of knowledge from the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) to Imam Ali (PBUH) and then to their descendants, thereby negating any possibility of non-divine selection of the Imam. The Imam further described Imamate as a divine caliphate in which "the reins of religion, the order of Muslims, the well-being of the world, and the honor of the believers" are held, and every ruling, such as prayer, fasting, jihad, etc., is perfected based on the acceptance of the principle of Imamate.

In another section, various characteristics of imamate are beautifully likened to the sun, moon, stars, sky, earth, intimate companion, father, brother, and so on. It refers to the Imam's vast knowledge and some of his prominent qualities, such as being a guide towards God and a defender of His commands, the divine and inspired nature of the Imam's knowledge, and his being a source of wisdom and knowledge.

The third axis of Imam al-Rida's (PBUH) words emphasizes the Imam's infallibility from any impurity and ugliness, error and mistake, and possessing special knowledge to stay away from defilement.

What is consistently emphasized in all the conclusions of this firm argument by the Imam and considered a challenge is the phrase 'So who is it who can attain the knowledge of the Imam or have the ability to choose him?' Comparing this viewpoint with what was previously quoted from Ma'mun al-Abbasi highlights the clarity of the Imamiyyah perspective on the selection of the Imam and his high position. This consolidated approach within the Shia community and the general Islamic society, as it appears, is drawn from the same terminology of the early period and the explanations of the previous era, forming a comprehensive knowledge system.

From the Era of Imam al-Jawad (PBUH) to the Beginning of the Occultation (Continuation of Thought)

In this period, the consolidation of knowledge and its functions takes shape with the preparation for the era of occultation. The Shia community, with its vast geographical expanse, scientific heritage from the previous era, scholarly institutions, intellectuals, scholars, etc., faces a unique experience in the matter of imamate. Attention to certain aspects, such as political pressures and the resulting distance of the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT) from the masses, the average age of Imams reaching Imamate in this period, which was around ten years, and its acceptance in the Shia community along with the support of elites and prominent figures like Ali ibn Ja'far, indicate the persistence and continuation of the concept of Imamate to such an extent that it can be utilized for a significant purpose.

Similarly, the incident of Yahya ibn Aktham and the statement of Ma'mun, the Abbasid caliph, regarding the extent of the Imam's knowledge also indicate public awareness of the concept of imamate. Of course, this does not mean overlooking deviant movements and certain tendencies, such as the Ghali (extremist) movement. However, it is fair to say that linking any movement or trend that arose among Shias to the unspoken dimensions of Imamate is incorrect, as the nature of the claims of these groups indicates motivations beyond the issue of Imamate. However, two events can be mentioned in the context of clarifying the discussions on Imamate during this period, emphasizing what has been said so far. These two important events are: a comprehensive explanation of the attributes of the imam; and the introduction of the concept of the occultation of the twelfth imam.

A Comprehensive View of the Imam's Attributes

As we know, during this period, the Ahl al-Bayt's (PBUT) scientific schools were established in various cities of Iran, and therefore, scientific circles and discussions on various topics flourished. The topic of Imamate, like other doctrinal issues, held a special place in these

discussions, and their challenging conversations were repeatedly examined and criticized, and various books were written on this subject. Some of these things were Imam al-Jawad's (PBUH) many debates and letters about theology with the two Askari Imams (PBUT), as well as reports about the Imamate and criticisms of stories that praised the first three caliphs. Alongside these, the writing of books proving Shia beliefs and refuting the opinions of opponents by the companions of the Askari Imams (PBUT), such as Thabit ibn Muhammad and Ibn Ishkib, increased during this period.

The writing of the book "Basair al-Darajat" and the publication of Kufi hadiths by Ali ibn Ibrahim and his father, which constitute a significant portion of the discussions in the book "al-Hujjah" from the esteemed book "al-Kafi," took place during this period. This indicates the maturity of the Shia scholarly community and the growth of their scientific approach.

However, the most important reported charter regarding the fundamental ideas of Shia Imamate emerged in the form of the Ziyarat Jame'ah from Imam al-Hadi (PBUH). Musa ibn Abdullah Nakh'i requested the Imam to teach him a Ziyarah (supplication for visitation) that, in addition to having eloquent text, would be suitable for the visitation of any Imam and encompass the attributes of the Imam. Therefore, in this Ziyarah, more than two hundred virtues and merits of the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT) are mentioned.

By examining the content of this Ziyarah, three important and fundamental axes can be identified: divine monotheism, divine proof (Hujjah), and imamate, along with the position that God has designated for the imam.

In this Ziyarah, initially, by saying "Allahu Akbar" (God is Great) a hundred times, greatness and majesty are attributed to God. In the opening sentences of this Ziyarah, after testifying to the oneness and unity of God, three other testimonies—the testimony of God, the angels, and the possessors of knowledge—are also mentioned as witnesses. These points were also mentioned in the early period, especially in the reports of Nahj al-Balagha and Sahifa al-Sajjadiyya. In this Ziyarah, with various expressions, the position of the Hujjah in the divine system is emphasized.

In the dimension of imamate, the etiquette of conversing with the imam is taught. The Ziyarah begins with salutations and greetings to the Imam, and after enumerating some of his attributes in explaining the concept of imamate and its connection to politics, which is one of the necessities for a deep understanding of the event of Ghadir, it openly mentions leadership and statesmanship as qualities and aspects of the Infallible Imams (PBUT).

Also, in explaining the concepts of allegiance (tawalla) to the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT) and disassociation (tabarra) from their enemies, the Imam refers to the content of narrations like Ghadir, Safinah, etc. and addresses the topic of Mahdism (belief in the awaited saviour). This, considering the possibility of the Ziyarah being disseminated, indicates the acceptance of this topic among Shias.

Among the most important topics of this Ziyarah are the following:

- The relationship of the Imams (PBUT) with God and the position of God in the view of the Infallible Imams (PBUT)
- The duty of the Infallibles towards the religion of God
- The legitimacy of the Imams and their inseparability from the truth, and that those who turn away from them will fall into error.
- The vast mercy of the Imam
- The appointment of the Imams by God and their responsibility for guiding people
- Their role as intermediaries between creation and the Creator
- The infallibility and purity of the Imams from defilement
- Their extensive divine knowledge and superhuman stations
- The correct explanation of the position of the Infallibles in the system of creation

- Attention to the devotional and political record of the Infallibles
- Emphasis on allegiance (tawalla) and disassociation (tabarra) as important practices for Shias
- The similarity of all Imams (PBUT) in their abilities
- The general understanding of the lack of distinction between the Imams (PBUT)
- The role of the Infallible Imams (PBUT) as intermediaries between creation and the Creator

The Occultation of the Twelfth Imam and the Organization of Representation

In previous discussions, it was mentioned that the general familiarity of Shias with the concept of the Occultation of the Twelfth Imam dates back to earlier years. However, in this period, understanding this concept gained significant importance due to the inaccessibility of the Imams and the management of Shia affairs through the consolidation of the organization of representation.

Although some narrations from the Imams (PBUT) describe the twelfth successor of the Prophet as the establisher of a comprehensive government, the upholder of justice, and possessing other specific qualities, they still emphasize the general inability to see that Imam. The words of Imam al-Jawad (PBUH) addressed to Abd al-Azim ibn Abdullah al-Hasani, describing the attributes of the Occult Imam, are a clear example of this.

The efforts of the Imams (PBUT), especially Imam al-Askari (PBUH), to maintain indirect communication with the Shias, particularly through appointing deputies and representatives who were generally prominent figures among the Imamiyyah and referring the general Shia community to them, clearly indicate the groundwork and normalization for the era of occultation. This is while in previous periods, especially in the first and second periods, direct access to the Imams (PBUT) was considered important, and there were no restrictions from their side on meeting them, except in special cases. However, in the later period, due to various aforementioned factors and the importance of the occultation of the twelfth imam, the process of meeting and referring to the imam shifted to meeting with scholars and representatives.

The reported example in Sheikh Tusi's book "al-Ghaybah" clearly illustrates the progression of this matter during the time of the Tenth Imam. In response to Ahmad ibn Ishaq's question about whom to follow and whose commands to obey since access to the Imam was not always possible, Imam al-Hadi (PBUH) instructed him to obey the representative in that region, whose words were the same as the Imam's.

Based on this, only a limited number of Shia elites could meet the Twelfth Imam (may Allah hasten his reappearance). Even in some cases, the Imam spoke to his Shias from behind a curtain.

Nevertheless, the abundance of reports regarding the Twelfth Imam indicates that the Imamate's authority emphasized the succession of Imam al-Askari (PBUH) and the characteristic of this successor being hidden from people's sight during this period. Therefore, except for specific and justifiable cases, there was no doubt among Shias about this matter. Shias quickly questioned the few false claims for Imam al-Askari's (PBUH) succession, sometimes using the same criteria set forth in earlier eras, such as enquiring about legal and illegal matters, etc. These claims were unable to harm the united body of the Shia community and its prevailing thought.

The efforts of one of Imam al-Hadi's (PBUH) sons, named Ja'far, to justify his behavior and write letters to some Imamiyyah companions were thwarted by the wisdom of Ahmad ibn Ishaq al-Ash'ari and the decree of the Imam of the Time (may Allah hasten his reappearance). The Imam, in this letter, refers to expressions similar to the Ziyarat Jame'ah Kabir. The incident of the two envoys from Qom and their encounter with Ja'far, the brother of Imam al-

Askari (PBUH), also illustrates this reality. Instances like these clearly demonstrate that, due to the teachings from the Imams (PBUT), the Shias were well-acquainted with the nuances and details of the concept of imamate. With ample knowledge and the ability to respond to doubts, they underwent a sixty-year training period to prepare for the long era of occultation.

Conclusion

Undoubtedly, the role of historical elements (political, social, cultural, and, in some cases, economic) in the process of explaining the beliefs of the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT), which are rooted in the Quran and Sunnah, is undeniable. Considering all these elements simultaneously in the four periods of the lives of the Ahl al-Bayt (PBUT), it reveals that a process of gradual elaboration was followed in the clarification of beliefs, through which the divine and prophetic teachings were disseminated without any alteration in content. In the first period, the emphasis of the Prophet (PBUH) and the Imams (PBUT) was on establishing the concept of imamate. In this period, the lack of alignment among historical elements stands out as the most significant factor hindering the in-depth dissemination of knowledge. In contrast, during the era of Imams Ja'far al-Sadiq and Muhammad al-Baqir (PBUT), the alignment of all political, social, cultural, and economic elements led to the formation and flourishing of knowledge. In the third period, although political conditions were unfavorable for a long time, the short-lived event of Imam al-Rida's (PBUH) crown prince affair partially compensated for this deficiency, and the consolidation and refinement of thought reached their peak. Finally, during the era of the later Imams, the ideas explained in previous periods were utilized as a knowledge system to prepare the vast Shia community, with abundant knowledge and the ability to respond to doubts, for the long period of occultation through a sixty-year training period.

References

1. Ibn Athir, A. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 3, p. 64).
2. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ilal al-Shara'i* (Vol. 1, p. 248).
3. Nu'mani, M. ibn I. (n.d.). *Al-Ghaybah* (p. 44); Hakim Nishaburi, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Al-Mustadrak ala al-Sahihayn* (Vol. 2, p. 171).
4. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 205); Suyuti, A. ibn A. B. (n.d.). *Al-Jami' al-Saghir* (Vol. 2, p. 161).
5. Tirmidhi, M. ibn I. (n.d.). *Sunan al-Tirmidhi* (Vol. 5, p. 637); Hakim Nishaburi, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 3, p. 126).
6. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Amali* (p. 307).
7. Ri-Shahri, M., et al. (n.d.). *Mus'ad al-Imam Ali ibn Abi Talib (PBUH)* (Vol. 2).
8. Haythami, A. ibn A. B. (n.d.). *Majma' al-Zawa'id wa Manba' al-Fawa'id* (Vol. 7, p. 81).
9. Mufid, M. ibn M. (n.d.). *Amali* (p. 214); Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, pp. 187, 346).
10. Ibn Asakir, A. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 3, p. 72).
11. Ibn Hajar, A. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 4, p. 467).
12. Majlisi, M. B. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 36, p. 267).
13. Maqrizi, T. al-D. (n.d.). *Imta' al-Asma* (Vol. 5, p. 376); Shushtari, Q. N. (n.d.). *Ihqaq al-Haqq* (Vol. 9, p. 391).
14. Majlisi, M. B. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 24, p. 88); Nu'mani, M. ibn I. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 53).
15. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Al-Amali* (Vol. 1, p. 75).
16. Ibn Hajar, A. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 52); Dhahabi, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Tarikh al-Islam* (Vol. 1, p. 286).

17. Ibn Kathir, I. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 7, p. 346); Haythami, A. ibn A. B. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 9, p. 109).
18. Nasa'i, A. ibn S. (n.d.). *Al-Sunan al-Kubra* (Vol. 5, p. 132); Tayalisi, S. ibn D. (n.d.). *Musnad Tayalisi* (p. 111); Ibn Abi Shaybah, A. B. (n.d.). *Al-Musannaf* (Vol. 7, p. 504).
19. Amini, A. H. (n.d.). *Al-Ghadir* (Vol. 1, p. 152).
20. Buhri, A. (n.d.). *Awa'lim al-Ulum* (p. 629).
21. Hilali, S. ibn Q. (n.d.). *Kitab Salim ibn Qays* (p. 789).
22. Amini, A. H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 2, p. 80).
23. Ibn Kathir, I. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 7, p. 332).
24. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ma'ani al-Akhbar* (p. 67); Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Amali* (p. 212).
25. Sayyid Razi, M. ibn H. (n.d.). *Nahj al-Balaghah* (p. 512); Ibn Abi al-Hadid (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 19, p. 86); Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ilal al-Shara'i* (Vol. 1, p. 248).
26. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 214).
27. Ibn Asakir, A. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 21, p. 415).
28. Tusi, M. ibn H. (n.d.). *Amali* (p. 148).
29. Sayyid Razi, M. ibn H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Kh 2).
30. Mufid, M. ibn M. (n.d.). *Al-Ikhtisas* (p. 220).
31. Tabari, M. ibn J. (n.d.). *Tarikh al-Umam wa al-Muluk* (Vol. 5, p. 424).
32. Arbili, A. ibn I. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 147).
33. Tusi, M. ibn H. (n.d.). *Amali* (p. 569); Al-Imam Ali ibn al-Husayn (n.d.). *Al-Sahifa al-Sajjadiyya* (p. 216).
34. Kashshi, M. ibn U. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 176).
35. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 238); Tusi, M. ibn H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 697).
36. Waqidi, M. ibn S. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 74); Tabari, M. ibn J. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 5, p. 158).
37. Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Basair al-Darajat* (p. 502); Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 348).
38. Nu'mani, M. ibn I. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 129).
39. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Ma'ani al-Akhbar* (p. 101).
40. Maqrizi, T. al-D. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 11, p. 181).
41. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 310).
42. Kashshi, M. ibn U. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 124).
43. Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 104).
44. Saduq, M. ibn A. (n.d.). *Al-Khisal* (p. 644).
45. Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 307).
46. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 261).
47. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 1, p. 242); Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (pp. 151-162).
48. Journal of Hadith Andishe (1391). *53–69*.
49. Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (p. 151).
50. Kulayni, M. ibn Y. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (Vol. 4, p. 273).
51. Saffar, M. ibn al-H. (n.d.). *Ibid.* (pp. 143 and 240).
52. Al-An'am/59, Al-Naml/65, Al-Baqarah/23, Fatir/38, Al-Ma'idah/109, Al-An'am/73, Al-Tawbah/94 and 105, Al-Ra'd/9, Al-Mu'm